

RISK MITIGATION ON TUNA SUPPLIER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT: A PREVENTIVE COLLABORATIVE ACTION

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Abstract:

There has been growing research on risks mitigation on supply chain. However, to date, research investigating about risks mitigation on supply chain especially on supplier relationship management based on relational view is limited. Therefore, to fill this gap, this study aims to describe the risks, analyse them, and then formulate the risks mitigation through a relational view approach among the actors of the tuna supplier relationship management in East Java of Indonesia. The respondents of this study were actors, i.e.: the manager of agro-industry, fishermen, middlemen, academician, and government officers of the fishery department. The data were analysed through the integration of the Interpretive Structural Model (ISM)-House of Risk (HOR)-Analytical Network Process (ANP). The findings showed that there were some risk groups that fall to the category of driver power, such as bad weather, fish migration season, and the shortage of fish caught. The high-risk agents were the use of instinct in forecasting the weather and fish seasons, the lack of post-fishing cooling facilities, the use of instinct in determining fishing grounds, and the imbalance of the trading system. The priority of the recommended risk prevention actions from this study are sharing substantial knowledge about technology, investing in partner fishing gear, sharing substantial knowledge about innovation, making agreements with partners, and maintaining intensive interactions with partners. Stakeholders in the supply chain, i.e: the manufacturer, middlemen, fishermen need to collaborate in managing the risks to improve the competitiveness of the product.

Keywords: supply chain; supplier relationship management risk mitigation; relational view; tuna

1. Introduction

One of the fish type that has an important economic value is the tuna, especially the group of Tuna-Skipjack-Mackerel that is a part of the Schombroidea family. This is seen from the total production value of Indonesia for tuna is IDR 10,982,906,784,000, for the skipjack tuna is IDR 10,855,639,127,000, and for the mackerel tuna is IDR 9,665,484,975,000 (Central Bureau of Statistic East Java Province, 2020); (Ministry of Marine Affair and Fisheries, 2020). Meanwhile, for the export, tuna fish ranks second after the shrimp with the value of USD 176.63 million or 14.23% (Central Bureau of Statistic East Java Province, 2020); (Ministry of Marine Affair and Fisheries, 2020) , its contribution towards the global tuna fishery is 20% (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019). The supporting factors are: high suitability of Indonesian water as the habitat for the growth and development of tuna fish, warm temperature, feeds availability and Indonesian water as a migration path (Ministry of Marine Affair and Fisheries, 2020), this is also supported by the availability of human resources. It is recorded that 2,359,064

people or 0.8% of the total population of Indonesia are fishermen (Central Bureau of Statistic East Java Province, 2020); (Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, 2020); (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2019). With that, the commodity can be classified to have competitive value in the international market.

However, tuna fishery faces several complex problems like the sustainability; overfishing on one type of the tuna, the Southern Bluefin in the Indian Ocean (Ministry Marine Affairs and Fisheries, 2020) and the tuna fish group in East Java (Harahab, Abidin, Supriyadi, Wardani, & ..., 2021); the high level of fish migration; management and ecological system; as well as the critical path of global fishery of fish with high economic value (Guillotreau, Squires, Sun, & Compeán, 2017). Besides, there is a structure and relationship among the actors that are unique in the fishery sector in several regions of Indonesia, especially in East Java Province (Karningsih et al., 2018); (Royandi, 2019); (Kornitasari, Manzilati, & Efani, 2019); (Satria, 2015). The existence of the government regulation related to the Fish Auction Place also contributes to the inefficiency of the fish supply chain, among those are the requirement to deposit a large amount of money for the auction participant that causes the limited number of participants. If we analyze it deeper, it is found that essential problems in the essential issue in the supply chain of the tuna fish lay on the upstream subsystem known as the Supplier Relationship Management (SRM), which is the point from the processor until the fish supplier. Previous reference shows that SRM significantly influences the supply chain as a whole (Kavale, 2016). The problem on SRM of tuna fish is found related to various uncertainties or business process risks and disintegrated risk management.

Previous researches on the risk were conducted on several themes, such as the identification of main risks on shrimp farming focusing on the quality, quantity, price and shipping time (Nasution, Arkeman, Soewardi, & Djatna, 2014), as well as diseases (Joffre, Poortvliet, & Klerkx, 2019). Therefore, the actors are suggested to apply a performance based contract (Nasution et al., 2014), and to control on the farmers characteristics (Joffre et al., 2019). On the milkfish farming, the highest risk was on the production and the suggestion for the farmer is to learn how to improve the production process and increasing the land investment capital (Akhmad Wasiur Rizqi & Moh Jufriyanto, 2020). Meanwhile, on tuna fishing in Indian Ocean, the mapped risks found were: shortage of fish caught, low fish quality, shortage of ice, lack of facility and infrastructure, lack of information on fishing area, bad weather, migration season, as well as the postponed production due to national or cultural holiday (Karningsih et al., 2018). (Parenreng & Nyoman Pujawan, PD Karningsih, 2016) developed a tuna locating system in Indian Ocean to mitigate the main risk through an investment in goods flow facility. In a supply chain, the actors are interconnected as they need to have a bonding to be able to control the possible risks effectively. However, the previous researchers have not sufficiently explain the relational perspective in managing the risks.

Relational is essential for the continuity of a business supply chain. According to (Hallikas, Karvonen, Pulkkinen, Virolainen, & Tuominen, 2004), the dependency among companies will improve the openness of them to the risks of other companies. According to (Al-Abdallah, Abdallah, & Bany Hamdan, 2014), supplier partnership/development and supplier lead time

reduction on the SRM influences the performance of purchasing company in the manufacture field. Meanwhile, (Kobayashi, 2014) mentioned that a particular characteristic of a car industry in Japan can get them, or as the prerequisite, to achieve competitive advantage with the relational perspective. According to (Dyer & Singh, 1998), there are four sources of inter-organizational relationship, i.e: 1) relation on specific assets; 2) knowledge sharing routines; 3) complementary resources/capabilities; 4) effective governance.

This study focuses on risk management on SRM of tuna with high economic value in the tuna group. The actors involved in SRM have the opportunity to face various types of risks and each person has a unique behavior to deal with these risks. Thus, this research aims to describe the risks on the SRM of tuna, analyze the risks and recommend the preventive action in managing the risks using the relational view approach.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study location. This study was carried out in three regencies, i.e.: Malang, Pacitan and Trenggalek as a centre of tuna in East Java. The study location show in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Location map in East Java Province, Indonesia

The Researchers explore and explain how the actors on the upstream subsystem involved on the business of capture fishery in managing the risks. The respondents consisted of the business actors of the fishery in one SRM network of tuna in East Java.

The agro-industry of the tuna processor as the focal firm was chosen using purposive sampling based on the business scale with the strategic contribution for the national income, also known as large scale. Meanwhile, the middlemen (tier 2) were chosen using snowball sampling based on connection with the tuna processor. The fishermen (tier 1) were chosen using snowball sampling based on connection with the middlemen. The supporting institution were those who support the tuna supply.

The data was collected through interviews and filling out questionnaires. The respondents, representing the actors of the supply chain consisted of: fishermen who their own vessel (land chief), vessel captain (sea chief) and the middlemen in coast area of Sendangbiru of Malang Regency, Prigi Coast of Trenggalek Regency and Tamperan Coast of Pacitan Regency, the

manager of raw material on the fish processing industry of Pasuruan Regency, the distributor of the tuna processed products, academician from the Faculty of Fishery and Marine Science of Brawijaya University, governmental official from the Ministry of Marine and Fishery, and Department of Fishery and Animal Husbandry of the Regency.

Data Analysis.

The data was analysed in stages using some tools of analysis. The risk identification was carried out using the integration of Interpretive Structural Modelling (ISM) – House of Risk 1 (HOR), while the recommended risk mitigation and control used the Analytical Network Process (ANP) – House of Risk 2 (HOR). The integration of the ISM-HOR-ANP methods is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The Integration of ISM-HOR-ANP methods

Intepretive Structural Modelling (ISM)

The ISM method is used to arrange the model of connections among the risks and identify the causes of the risks in the supply chain. ISM is a technique where the elements are interconnected directly and indirectly that is then structured into a systematic and comprehensive model through the directed graph (Attri, Dev, & Sharma, 2013).

The phase of ISM are 1) making the structural self interaction matrix (SSIM); 2) constructing the reachability matrix (RM) from the SSIM and checking the transitivity; 3) determining the grade of partitioning on the RM; 4) constructing the canonical matrix; 5) illustrating the diagraph; 6) constructing the ISM model. Then, according to (Pfohl, H.C; Gallus, P; Thomas, 2011), to understand the relationship between the risk even and the risk agents, the risk agent, then between the ISM and HOR are integrated. The output of the ISM is then used as the input for the next two steps in the Phase 1 of HOR method.

House of Risk (HOR) Phase 1

The risk that have been identified through the ISM is then analyzed using the HOR. HOR is a method that combines the Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA) and House of Quality (HOQ) (Pujawan & Geraldin, 2009). The phases of the HOR consist of HOR 1 and HOR 2.

HOR 1 is done to determine the sequence based on the Aggregate Risk Potential (ARP), that is calculated using Equation 1.

$$ARP_j = O_j \sum_i S_i R_{ij} \quad (1)$$

O_j is the probability of frequency of occurrence of risk agent j . S_i is the degree of severity due to risk event, R_{ij} is the correlation between the risk agent j and risk event i . The correlation value between the risk agent and risk event is 0, 1, 3 and 9, with the sequence of relationship ranging from “no correlation”, “low”, “medium”, and “high”.

The sequence of HOR fase 1 are 1) the scoring on the degree of severity, this is gained from the ISM method on the previous phase. The scale uses 1-10 as the score, with 1 means there is no impact, and 10 means dangerous impact; 2) scoring the degree of emergence of the risks causes that indicate the frequency of a risk to occur with the scale of 1-10; 3) scoring the correlation between the risk according to the respondents, with the scale of 0, 1, 3, 9; which mean “no correlation”, “weak”, “medium”, “high”; 4) determining the aggregate risk potential (ARP) and 5) illustrating the Pareto diagram to determine the priority risks.

Analytical Network Process (ANP)

The phase of the risk analysis on the actors is done to find out the risks that are necessary to handle and what preventive action is recommended for the risk, that is done to improve the competitive value of the tuna processed product. On this research, the approach used to achieve the objective is the ANP. ANP is an analysis tool that is able to represent the degree of importance of various parties in considering the dependence relationship among the criteria or even the sub-criteria.

The ANP method is a development from the AHP method, which is by improving the weakness of AHP in term of the capability in accommodating the relationship between the criteria or alternative (Saaty, T. L. dan Vargas, 2006). The ANP method has three (3) basic principles, decomposition, comparative scoring, and composition from the hierarchy or the synthesis from the priority. The principle of decomposition is applied to create a structure on the complex issue to become a hierarchy structure or a network of cluster, sub-cluster, sub-sub-cluster, and so on. In other word, decomposition is putting an issue into the ANP structure.

By using the ANP method, it can determine several priorities, the priority from the source of risk and type of risk that is faced by the supply chain, it can also find out the priority from the source of relationship based on the resources of the company that can influence the risk management on the supply chain. From the result of the prioritization of these factors, it can become a guideline in managing the risk in the supply chain that might possibly happen. The prevention from this risk will give the opportunity and benefit because it can minimize the loss that causes the financial loss for the company and its partner in the supply chain.

In this research, the model consists of two level of networking, a) Top Level Network: Risk Analysis and b) Sub Network: Alternative for Risk Management. The phase in the ANP method is the following: 1) Creating a Model Construction; 2) Creating the matrix of paired

comparison; 3) Creating the super-matrix; 4) Calculating the weight of importance from the cluster and node.

House of Risk (HOR) Phase 2

The next step is to integrate the ANP and the HOR phase 2 to determine the prioritized preventive action for the risk mitigation and the prevention. The phases are inserting the risk agent into the ANP to determine what preventive action that can be recommended to the business actors. The connections among each of the risk prevention are then inputted into the software of Superdecision to gain the ANP model.

The phases of HOR 2 are 1) designing of the preventive action ~~treatment~~ for mitigation on the risk event of HOR phase 1; 2) evaluating the correlation between the risks and the preventive action ~~treatment~~ for the mitigation or prevention by the respondents. With the measurement scale of 0, 1, 3, 9, which indicates if there is no correlation, or when the correlation is weak, medium, or high (Pujawan & Geraldin, 2009); 3) evaluating the level of difficulty of the mitigating preventive action with the scale of 3, 4, 5, that indicates that it is easy to apply, challenging or even difficult (Pujawan & Geraldin, 2009); 4) determining the ratio of effectiveness towards the difficulty (ETD) as the base to determine the priority of the mitigating preventive action that is recommended; 5) illustrating a Pareto diagram for the mitigating and preventing preventive action that is recommended. The output for the HOR phase 2 indicates that the prioritized preventing and mitigating preventive action that is recommended for all the business actors.

In this research, the classification of risk is mapped using SCRI (supply chain risk identification) based on the SCOR (supply chain operational reference) business framework. However, this research choose to use several dimensions in the SCOR, “sources”, “make”, and “deliver” because the risks on the dimension of “plan” are assumed to be included in other dimensions. Meanwhile, the dimension of “return” is not used in the risks analysis because this research focuses on the relationship among the processors, middlemen and fishermen.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Risk Identification

This research focuses on the business process, beginning from the “source” that consists of fishing, and trading, the “make” is the production or processing, the “deliver” is the distribution from the processors to the distributors, and the “enable” is the business supporting process for tuna in the form of funding and institutional support. Based on the interview results with the business actors, there are 18 risk events identified, presented in Table 1. Then, the ISM method is used to see the interconnection among those risks.

Table 1. The Identification of Risk Event

Business Process	Sub Process	Risk Event	Code
SOURCE: Fishing	Fulfillment of Raw Material	Shortage on the quantity of fish caught	E1
		Discrepancy on the quality of the caught before trade	E2
		Inaccurate size of fish caught	E3
	Natural and Social Environment	Inaccurate in predicting of bad weather	E4
		Inaccurate in predicting fish migration season	E5
		Cultural Holiday	E6
SOURCE: Trading	Trade of fish as raw material	Shortage of fish in quantity as the raw materials in the trade	E7
		The shortage of quality of fish as raw material in trade	E8
		Fluctuation of fish price	E9
MAKE: Processing	Production process	Shortage in production quantity	E10
		Discrepancy in product quality	E11
DELIVER: Distribution		Decline of product quality in delivery	E12
		Delay in delivery	E13
		Marketing	Fluctuation in demand
Dropping of world price of fish	E15		
ENABLE: Support	Financial	Discrepancy in capital return based on deal	E16
	Institutional	Discrepancy of regulation in the trade at dock	E17
		Unharmonious relationship with the partners	E18

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

On the business process of “sourcing”, which is the activity of fish catching, especially on the sub-process of fulfilling the materials, 3 risk events were identified. Those are the lacking in quantity of fish caught, the pre-trading fish quality, and the inaccurate size of fish caught. On the sub-process of environment and social, 4 risk events were identified, bad weather, fish migrating season and cultural holiday. On the activity of trading, especially in the sub-process of trading of raw materials, 3 risk events were identified, the lacking of the quantity of raw material in trade, fish quality and the fish price fluctuation.

On the business process of “making”, which is in the activity of production especially the sub-process of production, there were 2 risk events identified, the lacking in product quantity, and the inaccurate product quality.

On the business process of “delivering”, on the activity of product distribution, especially in the sub-process of marketing, 4 risk events were identified, which are decreasing quality of products in delivery, delay of delivery, and the dropping of world fish price. On the business process of “enable” on the supporting activity of SRM, especially on the sub-process of financial, one risk even was identified, which was the inaccurate capital return with the deal. Meanwhile, on the sub process of institutional, there were two risk events, the discrepancy of regulation in the trade and the lacking of harmony of relationship with the partners.

3.2 Interpretive Structural Modelling (ISM)

The results of data processing with the ISM, based on the driver power and dependence power, there are variables in the groups of autonomous, linkage, dependent and independent. Group 1 is autonomous that has the power in influencing the weak one and strong resistance from influence as well. On this research, there were 10 risk events classified in the group of autonomous, E2 (lacking in quality of fish before the trade), E7 (lacking in quantity of fish before the trade), E14 (demand fluctuation), E3 (discrepancy of fish size with the demand), E6 (cultural holiday), E8 (discrepancy of fish quality in trade), E12 (discrepancy of quality of product in delivery), E13 (delay in delivery), E15 (the dropping of world price for fish), E16 (the return of capital that is not according to the deal) and E17 (discrepancy of the regulation of trade in the docks).

Meanwhile, group 2 is the “linkage” that is a group with the element that has the strong power in influencing and in resisting influence. From this research, apparently there was no risk event falls to the group of “linkage”.

There are 5 risk events in the group 4 or the “dependence”, E10 (lacking in the production quantity), E18 (unharmonious relationship of with the partners), E11 (discrepancy of the quality of processed product), E9 (fluctuation of fish price). The group 3 here is the group consists of the elements with the power in influencing the weak one, and is strong in resisting influence of others.

Eventually, the output that needs primary attention is on the group 4 that is namely the “independent” that consists of the elements with the power of influencing and is strong in resisting the influence of others. In this research, there were 3 risk events on the group of “independent”, E4 (bad weather), E5 (fish migration season), and E1 (discrepancy of the quantity of fish caught). The mapping of risk event from the ISM is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Driver Power Dependence Map

Table 2 below indicates the detailed position of the risk event on the particular quadrant based on the power to influence and to resist influence from the other. It is also to indicate the level of each risk events from the highest risk to the lowest risk.

Table 2. Driver-Power Dependence on Risk Event

Quadrant	Risk Event	Code	Level
Driver Power (IV)	Bad Weather	E4	Level 1
	Fish Migration Season	E5	Level 2
	Shortage on the quantity of fish caught	E1	Level 3
Autonomous (I)	Discrepancy of the quality of fish caught before the trade	E2	Level 4
	Shortage of raw material of fish during the trade	E7	Level 5
	Fluctuation of demand	E14	Level 6
	Discrepancy on the size of fish caught	E3	Level 7
	Cultural Holiday	E6	Level 7
	Discrepancy on the quality of fish caught during the trade	E8	Level 7
	Dropping of fish quality on delivery	E12	Level 7
	Delay on delivery	E13	Level 8
	Dropping on the world price of fish	E15	Level 7
Dependence Power (III)	Discrepancy of capital return based on a deal	E16	Level 7
	Discrepancy of regulation in the dock trading	E17	Level 7
	Fluctuation of fish price during the trade	E9	Level 8
	Shortage of production quantity	E10	Level 8
	Discrepancy on the quality of processed products	E11	Level 8
	Unharmonious relationship with the partners	E18	Level 8

The output from the ISM method in the form of key factors is used for HOR phase 1 data processing. The ISM and HOR-1 integrated model is illustrated on Figure 4 as follow. From the HOR1, it is acquired that the sequence of key risks, then the risk is connected to the causes.

Figure 4: ISM-HOR1 integrated model

The evaluation was carried out based on the degree of severity of each risk events. The probability of the risk agents to occur, the correlation between the risk even and the risk agent. Then, the calculation of the aggregate risk potentials (ARP) of these factors was carried out. The evaluation and calculation results is presented on Table 3.

Table 3. The calculation of ARP on HOR 1

Risk Event (Ei)	Risk Agent (Aj)														Severity (Si)	
	A7	A24	A1	A8	A2	A16	A4	A5	A9	A10	A13	A14	A17	A18		
E4	9															7
E5			5	9												5
E1	3		3	3												7
E2								9								7
E7					5						5					5
E14												3				1
Occurance (Oj)	7	3	7	7	3	1	1	7	1	5	5	1	3			
ARP	588	0	322	462	75	0	0	441	0	0	140	0	0			
Rank	1	7	4	2	6			3			5					

The result of ARP calculation, it indicates that the highest 5 risk agents are “using instinct in predicting weather” (A7), “using instinct in predicting the fish season” (A8), “discrepancy of cooling facility after fishing” (A5), “using instinct to determine area of fishing” (A1) and “unfairness on the trading system” (A13). The score of ARP and the percentage of ARP on the risk agents are presented on Table 4.

Table 4. The score of ARP and the percentage of ARP

Aij	Risk Agent	ARPi _j	Presentase ARPi _j (%)
A7	Using instinct to predict the weather	588	28,99
A8	Using instinct to predict the fish season	462	22,78
A5	Discrepancy on the cooling cafility after fishing	441	21,75
A1	Relying on the instrinct to determine fishing ground	322	15,88
A13	Unfairness on the trading system	140	6,90

The score of ARP on the risk agents are illustrated on the Pareto diagram on Figure 5. From the figure, it can be seen that the highest score of risk agent is for the “using instinct to predict the weather”.

Figure 5. Pareto Diagram

3.3 House of Risk (HOR) dan Analytical Network Process (ANP)

The objective of phase of HOR2 is to formulate a plan of preventive action and risk mitigation. Based on the list of alternative preventive actions, a study for measuring the weight and priority of each preventive action needs to be carried out. The objective of this study is to increase the accuracy of the goals to be achieved for reducing the frequency and the impact of the risks.

The method of ANP is used to see the connection by considering the output of ISM and HOR1. The experts are asked to fill the questionnaires of paired comparison and the results are then inserted by the researcher to the software of Superdecision. The following figure is the display of the ANP model.

Figure 6. ANP model using Relational View

From the result of the data processing in the ANP, we obtain the weight and score priority of each treatment for the risk mitigation (figure 7).

Here are the priorities.

Name	Normalized by Cluster	Limiting
1.1 Investasi untuk Kedekatan Lokasi	0.26093	0.036540
1.2 Penyertaan Modal Pada Peralatan Produksi	0.23285	0.032608
1.3 Interaksi Intensif dg SDM Mitra	0.50623	0.070892
4.1 Perjanjian Pihak Ketiga melalui Kontrak L~	0.39947	0.134210
4.2 Kesepakatan Sendiri	0.35163	0.118137
4.3 Relasi Informal Tanpa Ikatan	0.24890	0.083624
3.1 Penggabungan Aset Unik	0.23603	0.058057
3.2 Penggabungan Kapabilitas Unik	0.42304	0.104057
3.3 Penggabungan Intangible Aset Unik	0.34092	0.083858
2.1 Pertukaran Pengetahuan ttg Teknologi	0.29708	0.082594
2.2 Pertukaran Pengetahuan ttg Inovasi	0.29945	0.083252
2.3 Pertukaran informasi ttg Pasar	0.40347	0.112170

Figure 7. The Prioritized Preventive Action for Risk Mitigation Based on the Weight of ANP Model

The next phase is the HOR2 that aims to identify the prioritized action to optimize the effectiveness of the attempt to mitigate the risk based on the resources and the relation among the actors. On table 5, the main risk agents are presented as the focus of the search for the solution alternative to mitigate the risk. Then, the priority of the preventive action in mitigating the risks are integrated between the result of the of the ANP and the score of effectiveness towards the difficulty in implementing an action (ETDK). The recommended action to the business actors are those with the higher ratio score.

Table 5. The calculation of ETDK to HOR2

Risk Agent (Aj)	Risk Agent Action (Aj)												ARPi
	PA1	PA2	PA3	PA4	PA5	PA6	PA7	PA8	PA9	PA10	PA11	PA12	
A7		7	1	9	5		1	3		3	3	3	588
A8		7	1	9	5		1	3					462
A5		9	5	7	7		3						441
A1		7	1	9	5		1	3			5		322
A14			5	3	3					9	7	1	140
TEK=ARPi*Aj		13573	4277	15855	10367		2695	4116		3024	4354	1904	
DK	9	5	7	5	5	7	7	7	9	5	7	9	
ETDK		2715	611	3171	2073		385	588		605	622	212	
Rank		2	5	1	3						4		

From this research, it is acquired that there are 12 prioritized prevention actions. Meanwhile, the mitigating actions that ranks the highest are sharing the substantial knowledge about technology (PA4), investment on assets based on the partner need (PA2), sharing the substantial knowledge about innovation (PA5), creating deals with the partners (PA11) and creating an intensive interaction with the partners (PA3).

4. DISCUSSION

The results of this study show a bond between one risk to the other, so they are grouped based on their power in influencing other risks. The risks that have greater power to influence other risks are 3 risk events in the independent group, namely E4 (bad weather), E5 (fish migration season) and E1 (Lack of quantity of fish caught). Based on the opinion of the actors, bad weather and fish migration season are risk events requiring attention. The two risk events are in the upstream sub-system, namely supplier-1 where the perpetrators are fishermen. Bad weather at sea and fish migration season are natural events. (Karningsih et al., 2018) and (Parenreng & Nyoman Pujawan, PD Karningsih, 2016) stated that from the risk mapping of tuna fisheries in Indian Ocean, it was found that a natural event was one of external environmental factors affecting fishing activities, which in turn could affect the quantity of fish caught and traded, as well as its distribution to the consumers.

This study also found some risk agents (from the greatest to the lowest), i.e.: the use of instinct for forecasting the weather” (A7); the use of instinct for predicting the fish season (A8); the discrepancy of cooling facility after fishing” (A5); the use of instinct for determining the fishing ground (A1); and the “imbalance/unfair system of trading” (A13) on the supply chain of tuna.

These causes are then looked for alternative actions to prevent possible occurrences in the future. From the causes of risk that have been identified, then proceed with ANP to give weights and HOR2 to find priorities for prevention and risk mitigation. In this study, the recommended preventive actions, in order of highest priority to lowest, include sharing substantial knowledge about technology (PA4), investing in tools for partners (PA2), sharing substantial knowledge about innovation (PA5), making deals with partners (PA11).) and establish intensive interactions with partners (PA3). Visually this is illustrated in the alternative risk control for tuna SRM in the following Figure 8.

The risk agents are then analyzed to find alternative actions to prevent the probability of occurrence in the future. The identified risk agents then analysed by using the ANP to give weight and HOR2 for finding the prioritized treatment in mitigating and preventing the risks. In this research, the recommended preventive treatments, from the highest to the lowest score, are “sharing the substantial knowledge about technology” (PA4), “investment on the tools for the partners” (PA2), “sharing the substantial knowledge about the innovation” (PA5), creating a deal with the partners (PA11) and “creating an intensive interaction with the partners” (PA3). Visually, those recommendations are illustrated in the alternative of risk management on the SRM of the tuna on the Figure 8 as follow.

Figure 8. Risk Management on the SRM of Tuna

The lack of the knowledge in predicting the weather, fish migration season and the fishing ground efficiently and effectively causes the main risk events to occur in supply chain. It can be prevented by several alternatives of preventive action that is relational based among the actors as recommended in HOR phase 2. The processing company that plays a role as focal firm having a capital power can support the first supplier (fishermen) by sharing the knowledge on technology as well as innovation. The processing company can also invest some tools suited with the needs of the partners in term of technology and innovation in order to help their activity of fishing. The actors also need to make a mutually beneficial agreement for all parties and create an intensive interaction with the partners to produce a long-term cooperation. A certain supplier strategy (e.g. ordering large batches to decrease procurement costs or single-source suppliers with long contractual commitments) may be acceptable in a non-turbulent environment, it may be detrimental in a more turbulent one (e.g. in the presence of quick technological advances). (Trkman & McCormack, 2009).

It is inline with (Dovev Lavie, 2006), which mentions that the nature of relationship is far more important than the nature of resources in a networked environment to achieve the competitive advantage. The phenomena of a company based organization that tend to be individualistic like the ones used on the Resources Based View (RBV) (Barney, 1991); (Barney, 2012) needs adjustment along with the development of business world. The old RBV (Barney, 1991) emphasize on the company as an individual entity with the consequence of presenting only one internal side to strengthen the performance of the company. Meanwhile, in reality, the business actors cannot be separated from other actors, they are interconnected to achieve their business goal.

The actors of the supply chain can use their resources in their inter-organizational relationship. From the findings, it is showed that the prioritized preventive action in mitigating the risks on the supply chain of the tuna are, consecutively, “knowledge sharing by trading substantial

knowledge about technology” (PA4); “relation specific asset through investment on tools according to the needs of the partners” (PA2), “knowledge sharing through giving substantial knowledge about innovation” (PA5), and the “effective governance through creating a deal with the partners” (PA11) and creating an intensive interaction with the partners (PA3). Thus, it can be acquired that the findings of the research supports the proposition of (Dovev Lavie, 2006), who developed RBV to achieve the competitive advantage through relational view (Dyer & Singh, 1998) that is collaborated with the network resources (Ranjay Gulati, 1998). On the network resources, the main attention is on how that the resources that are attached to the alliance network of the companies create the alliance decision (Ranjay Gulati, 1998). From the data analysis result of this research, it is acquired that the source of the chosen relationship that is recommended to mitigate the risks is attached to the resources within the networking of the supply chain. There are actors and linkage in one supply chain, which the relationship can be empowered through forming commitment among the actors.

This finding brings the implication for the managers consider the relational aspects by utilizing the resources owned by the actors in taking decision to mitigate and prevent the risk based on the relationship of the actors in the SRM, which can improve the competitive value of the product and will be an opportunity for the continuation of the business in the long run. According to (Eegunjobi & Ngepah, 2022), the quality of the management on local institution can influence the participation on the global value chain in improving the trade. With the relational, then the quality of the management on the tuna supply chain can improve especially through the aspect of risk management.

Generally, the researchers constructed the preventive-collaborative action model to bridge the risk agents and the risk events in the supply chain. The actors need the awareness upon the consequence or the risk that might occur. The issue faced in a supply chain is the issue for all. Like in this case, the issue is the instability amount of fish supply as raw material, where this issue occurred because of various reasons like on the supplier party, the fishermen. Fishermen tend to use their instinct in predicting the weather that end up in inaccuracy in forecasting it, same goes about predicting the fish migration season that end up in the inaccuracy in predicting the movement of the fish and also about the fishing ground so that one might failed in determining the fishing ground, so that the fishermen may not optimized the fish caught. Along with that, then the second supplier, namely middlemen, also experience the shortage of number of fish to deliver to the processing company, so that the manufacture will face the issue in fulfilling their quota of raw material for the production.

The awareness upon the factors of risk agents can support the effort in mitigating the risk. In general, the Fishermen have this instinct to prevent or mitigate the risk naturally. However, if one only relies on instinct then the chance of risk events to occur is also bigger. The use of traditional methods to prevent several main risk events still dominate the behavior of the fishermen since they have the limitation in the skill they master, the limitation on the knowledge on technology and innovation, the limitation of capital to facilitate their needs facility for fishing. For that, it needs some preventive action that is collaborative, by involving

multi stakeholders that are related in this supply chain. The actors have the bigger capability so that they can share it to the parties in need.

So far, the only upstream subsystem to interact with the manufactures is the second supplier, which is the middlemen. In fact, the manufacturers have great capability to collaborate with actors in the upstream subsystem because they are large-scale company with strong capital. It means, they have capability to overcome the root of the problems in the supply chain. A big company can contribute to the society, especially those who need the support in business, in this case is the fishermen that needs the funding and knowledge for their role in catching fish. (Chen, Sohal, & Prajogo, n.d.), stated that long-term orientation and collectivism will strengthen relationship commitment and encourage information sharing. Meanwhile, the management of supply chain risks through coordination or collaboration among the supply chain partners so as to ensure profitability and continuity (Tang, 2006).

Apart from the manufacture, the other related parties also need to be more active in overcoming the problems of the fish supply, such as the government that have an ~~with~~ authority to issue, monitor and evaluate trade regulations. Besides, the researcher or the academician, as the independent party, can contribute to solving the problems through the feedback given to the government, the business actors as well as the society in general. The fishermen also need to be more active in seeking for information and knowledge to improve their competence and capability in supporting their main work as fishermen.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the ISM method, it show that there are three risk events that are on the quadrant of “driver power” with the great power to influence and great power in resisting influence from other risks, like bad weather, fish migration season, and the shortage in quantity of fish caught. Then based on the combined method of ISM, ANP and HOR, it is acquired that the risk agents, consecutively, are “using instinct to predict the weather”, “using instinct to predict the fish season”, ”the discrepancy of cooling facility after fishing”, “relying on their instinct to determine the fishing ground” and the “unfairness of the trading system on SRM of tuna”.

The prevention action that are prioritized, consecutively, are “sharing substantial knowledge about technology”, “investment on the tools based on the partner’s need”, “sharing the substantial knowledge about innovation”, “making deals with the partners”, and “creating an intensive interaction with the partners”.

For the actors in the SRM, it is suggested to conduct the preventions to manage the risk by prioritizing the relational action to improve the competitive advantage of the tuna products. Also, for the development of the knowledge, further research needs to be conducted to study the application of the RV concept in the risk management on the SRM as well as the supply chain of the agro-business of tuna so that it has a sustainable competitive value. The researchers are suggested to integrate ISM with the other quantitative methods so that it can overcome the difficulties should the matrix is too big.

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